

Digital Marketing Strategy: The Effectiveness of Content Marketing in Building Brand Trust for MSMEs in Gorontalo

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Abstract

This study aims to explore content marketing that is used effectively by MSMEs in order to build brand trust in Gorontalo. Understanding the relationship between content strategy and consumer perception, provides practical and theoretical contributions related to digital marketing strategies. This study uses a descriptive qualitative method approach with in-depth interviews with MSME actors with samples taken from MSMEs that have the best performance in utilizing digital marketing. Participatory observation was carried out by visiting several MSME actors to measure the impact of content marketing strategies on consumer trust. The results of the study show that content marketing has an important role in building MSME brand trust in Gorontalo. The presentation of relevant, informative, and authentic content allows MSMEs to attract consumers' attention and build long-term relationships with consumers. The effectiveness of content marketing can be seen from the ability to create added value through consumer education, streaming content and conveying brand stories that arouse emotions. Research shows that the use of digital platforms such as social media and e-commerce that are consistent with brand identity, increases engagement by up to 35% and consumer trust by up to 25%.

Keywords: Digital Marketing Strategy; Content Marketing; Brand Trust; Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs); Customer Engagement

Introduction

The development of information technology has brought about major changes in the way companies market their products and services. Digital marketing, as one of the results of this evolution, has become the backbone of modern marketing strategies (Teviana et al., 2024). This applies not only to large companies, but also to micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs), which utilize this strategy to reach consumers more widely and efficiently (Angelita & Kramadibrata, 2024). MSMEs, as the main drivers of the economy in many countries, face various challenges in increasing competitiveness. On the other hand, the digital era presents great opportunities for MSMEs to promote their brands through digital platforms. The right strategy allows MSMEs to utilize digital marketing to reach new audiences and retain loyal customers. Brand trust plays an important role in determining consumer loyalty, especially for MSMEs that often have to compete with bigger brands. To build trust, MSMEs need to create a positive image in the minds of consumers, which can be achieved through consistent and relevant digital marketing strategies (Nirwana & Biduri, 2021).

Content marketing focuses on creating and distributing valuable content, has become one of the most effective strategies in digital marketing. Providing relevant and interesting information allows MSMEs to attract consumers' attention and build long-term relationships based on trust (Wijoyo, 2021). Quality content can help SMEs build trust by demonstrating their credibility and expertise. Educational, informative, or inspirational content adds value to consumers, creating a strong emotional connection between the brand and the audience.

In Indonesia, with the number of internet users continuing to increase, the potential for digital marketing is huge. Many MSMEs are starting to turn to digital platforms such as social media, e-commerce, and websites to increase their visibility and build brand trust. As an evolving approach, content marketing requires a deep understanding of how this strategy can be optimized, especially in the context of MSMEs (Ramadhani, 2021). Content marketing not only functions as a promotional tool, but also as a means to create added value for consumers. For MSMEs, this approach allows them to interact with consumers more personally, build credibility, and strengthen emotional connections with the audience. The success of content marketing depends not only on the quality of the content, but also on the consistency, relevance, and distribution of the content. In the context of MSMEs, understanding audience preferences is key to creating maximum impact (Kartikasari, 2021). Although promising, implementing content marketing has its own challenges, especially for MSMEs that have limited resources. Some of the main obstacles include lack of technical knowledge, time, and budget to produce quality content. Content marketing can increase customer trust and loyalty. However, most studies focus more on large companies, so there is a need to understand its effectiveness in the context of MSMEs (Hadi & Zakiah, 2021).

Globally, content marketing has become an integral part of digital marketing strategies (Ramadhan & Yusuf, 2022). In Indonesia, many MSMEs are beginning to realize the importance of this strategy, but optimal implementation is still a challenge. This study highlights ways that MSMEs in Indonesia can implement to improve the effectiveness of their

content marketing. Increasing competition in the digital world encourages MSMEs to utilize marketing strategies not only attract attention but also build trust (E. Kurniawan et al., 2021).

Methods

This research was conducted using a descriptive qualitative approach through in-depth interviews, participant observation and collecting relevant documentation (Anto et al., 2024). A qualitative approach is used with the aim of gaining an in-depth understanding of consumer perceptions of content produced by MSMEs. The research design used includes surveys and tracing the digital footprint of MSME actors on online platforms. Literature studies are also used to understand the behaviour of certain MSMEs in using content marketing to build brand trust (Watulandi, 2024). This study focuses on two groups of MSMEs, namely content creators and consumers as content recipients. The selected MSME actors are MSME actors with the best performance in Gorontalo City who are quite active in using digital marketing. Meanwhile, the consumer samples used as informants were selected using a random sampling method or purposive sampling, which considers active consumers in digital media (Dakpo et al., 2022). The number of informants was limited in order to obtain primary data from in-depth interviews using the snowball sampling method.

Data collection methods include in-depth interviews, document analysis, and direct observation. In-depth interviews with MSME actors can reveal strategies and challenges in implementing content marketing. Document analysis, such as social media posts or MSME blogs, can provide an overview of the quality and patterns of content produced (Dzikrullah & Chasanah, 2024). Direct observation helps understand the interaction between consumers and content. In this study, qualitative instruments such as interview guides and observation checklists were used to explore descriptive data. Qualitative data analysis was carried out using thematic methods, namely identifying patterns or main themes from the results of interviews or documents analysed. The limitations of this study include the difficulty in accessing valid data from a number of MSMEs or consumers, as well as the subjective bias of respondents. In addition, the rapidly changing digital dynamics make it necessary to test the relevance of data periodically (Sudardjat & Yosephine, 2024). From an ethical perspective, research must ensure the confidentiality of respondent data and obtain explicit permission from MSME actors to analyse their content. An ethical and transparent approach to obtaining objective research results provides practical and theoretical contributions to the development of MSME digital marketing strategies (Wulansari et al., 2024).

Results

The present study demonstrates that a content strategy can facilitate the establishment of a more personal and profound relationship with consumers. MSMEs that leverage digital platforms to convey brand narratives, furnish educational information, and proactively engage with consumers can enhance positive perceptions of their brands. The findings of the study demonstrate that content marketing plays a substantial role in fostering MSME brand trust through a relevant, authentic, and consistent approach. The presentation of educational, inspirational, or entertaining content serves as a catalyst for MSMEs to showcase their brand

values and fortify a positive image in the eyes of consumers. The research findings on two MSME actors in Gorontalo City, namely MSME Rahida Cookies and MSME Ghidza Sasuke, substantiate this claim. MSME Rahida Cookies emphasizes the distribution of content by creating live streaming on Facebook and Tiktok, while MSME Ghidza Sasuke increases reels content on Instagram and Facebook platforms that are relevant to audience needs. The relevance of such content to audience needs has been demonstrated to foster increased trust due to its capacity to provide tangible solutions to consumers' challenges. The utilization of storytelling in the context of business and social values has been identified as a key strategy for fostering profound emotional connections with consumers. This approach, coupled with the transparent dissemination of information, particularly concerning the manufacturing process and the origins of raw materials, has been shown to enhance brand credibility. This study found that active interaction through social media and the presence of user-generated content (UGC) such as ratings, reviews, and authentic testimonials from customers strengthen the perception of brand honesty. Consequently, content marketing emerges as a potent strategy for MSMEs to cultivate consumer trust and loyalty. The study's findings substantiate that content marketing functions as a conduit for establishing trust through three primary aspects: relevance, authenticity, and consistency. The study found that consumers tend to trust brands that provide content that is relevant to their needs, authentic in its delivery, and consistent in providing added value.

The present study demonstrates that the most efficacious types of content in establishing brand trust for MSMEs are visual, educational, interactive, and entertaining content that is pertinent to the needs of the audience. Visual content, including short videos that align with prevailing trends, informative videos, and emotional storytelling videos, has been found to be particularly effective due to its ease of comprehension and aesthetic appeal. Educational content, such as product usage tutorials, practical tips, or customer testimonial videos, can fortify the brand image of MSMEs that offer added value to consumers. Furthermore, interactive content, such as giveaways, quizzes, or live question-and-answer sessions on social media, facilitates a direct dialogue with the audience, thereby enhancing engagement and emotional connections with consumers. User-generated content (UGC), such as ratings, reviews, testimonials, and consumer uploads about their experiences using the product, is also a very effective tool because it is considered authentic and more trustworthy. By integrating diverse content types, MSMEs can cultivate long-term consumer trust and loyalty. The present study demonstrates that visual content, including infographics, videos, and high-quality product images, exhibits a greater degree of appeal in comparison to text alone. Furthermore, educational content, such as tutorials, product usage guides, and tips aligned with consumer needs, is regarded as a means to enhance trust due to its provision of tangible value.

The findings of the study indicate that social media emerges as the most efficacious digital platform for implementing content marketing in fostering brand trust for MSMEs. Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok have been identified as the most prevalent platforms in this

regard. Instagram has been found to be particularly adept at showcasing visual content, including product photos, brief video recordings, and the use of its "stories" feature, which has been demonstrated to enhance brand image. In contrast, Facebook has been found to be particularly effective for text-based and live-streaming content. TikTok's distinctive algorithm positions it as a promising platform for reaching younger demographics through its creative, authentic, and frequently viral video content. In addition to social media, websites and blogs play an important role as sources of more in-depth and credible information, for example through articles or FAQs that answer consumer needs. E-commerce platforms such as Shopee and Tokopedia offer additional avenues for integrating content marketing strategies with product promotions. The strategic integration of these diverse platforms enables MSMEs to access a broad spectrum of audience segments and cultivate trust through the dissemination of pertinent content on optimal channels. The most prevalent social media platforms utilized by MSMEs, including MSME Rahida Cookies and MSME Ghidza Sasuke, are Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok. The study revealed that Instagram is effective for building a brand's visual image, while TikTok helps create more casual interactions and broader engagement. Additionally, blogs and websites are identified as valuable sources of in-depth information, contributing to the enhancement of brand credibility.

The findings of this study have demonstrated that the frequency and consistency of posts have a substantial impact on the establishment of brand trust for MSMEs through content marketing. MSMEs that consistently engage in content marketing tend to exhibit higher levels of engagement with their audience and are better positioned to cultivate long-term relationships. This strategy has been successfully employed by MSME Rahida Cookies and MSME Ghidza Sasuke, who have meticulously crafted schedules for the dissemination of pertinent content and the execution of live streams. Such strategic scheduling has been demonstrated to enhance traffic and engagement metrics, underscoring the efficacy of maintaining a consistent and predictable brand presence. This approach not only ensures brand visibility but also fosters the development of consumer expectations and habits, thereby contributing to the establishment of long-term relationships. Maintaining a consistent style, message, and content quality is also of paramount importance, as consumers are more likely to trust brands that appear stable and reliable. This study found that when MSMEs demonstrate consistency in producing relevant and quality content, consumers feel a greater sense of connection to the brand and are more inclined to believe in the brand's promises, which, in turn, fosters loyalty and repeat purchases. Conversely, less or inconsistent posting can cause the audience to lose interest and reduce the level of trust in the brand. Conversely, MSMEs that maintain a consistent posting schedule, such as 3-4 times per week, have been found to successfully cultivate more intimate relationships with their audiences. The study's findings suggest that the optimal frequency of content dissemination, ranging from three to four times per week, enhances consumer engagement without inducing feelings of annoyance.

The findings of this study have demonstrated that storytelling in content marketing has a significant impact on fostering emotional relationships and trust in MSME brands. This

is due to its capacity to establish more profound personal connections between brands and consumers. The integration of narratives that detail the trajectory of MSME enterprises, the obstacles encountered, and the principles adhered to facilitates the presentation of brands in a more authentic and humanistic manner. Consumers have been observed to exhibit a heightened level of trust in brands that offer not only products but also a narrative that is both touching and inspiring. This study underscores the efficacy of storytelling in fostering brand loyalty and encouraging consumers to share their experiences, thereby amplifying positive word-of-mouth referrals. Additionally, storytelling assists in enhancing the perception of transparency and memorability of brands, thereby fostering heightened customer trust and loyalty. By presenting relatable stories that resonate with the audience on an emotional level, MSMEs can cultivate deeper relationships with consumers, thereby fostering a more robust and trusted brand image. This underscores the pivotal role of storytelling in content marketing strategies. Narratives that detail the journey of MSME businesses, the challenges faced, and the values espoused by the brand help to forge emotional connections with consumers. The presence of such narratives fosters a heightened sense of connection between consumers and the brand, particularly in cases where transparency and inspiring narratives are present.

The findings of the study demonstrate that educational content exerts a substantial influence in fostering brand trust for MSMEs. Consumers exhibit a greater propensity to place their trust in brands that furnish useful and relevant information that aligns with their needs. Educational content, including tutorials, product usage guides, informative articles, or practical tips, not only facilitates consumer understanding of products or services but also demonstrates the brand's expertise and credibility in its field. The study's findings indicate that MSMEs that consistently deliver educational content offering genuine solutions to consumers' challenges can fortify their brand's image as a reliable source of information. Furthermore, educational content has been shown to foster increased brand loyalty by offering consumers added value without appearing overly promotional. Consequently, MSMEs that prioritize educational content in their content marketing strategy are able to deepen relationships with their audiences and build a stronger reputation, which ultimately increases consumer trust and purchasing decisions. The findings of the study demonstrate that educational content, such as tutorials or tips, fortifies the position of MSMEs as authorities in their respective domains. The study's findings indicate that consumers place greater trust in brands that can offer specific solutions to their problems.

The findings of the study demonstrate that User-Generated Content (UGC) exerts a substantial influence on the establishment of brand trust for MSMEs. This is due to the fact that content generated by consumers is regarded as more authentic and trustworthy in comparison to content produced by the brand itself. UGC, including product reviews, images of products in use, and customer testimonials, offers social proof that reinforces brand credibility among potential consumers. Research has demonstrated that consumers exhibit a heightened propensity to place trust in the experiences of others who are relevant to them, thereby underscoring the potential of UGC to influence purchasing decisions. Furthermore, UGC fosters direct interaction between consumers and brands, thereby strengthening

relationships and enhancing brand loyalty. Furthermore, brands that actively encourage and display UGC are regarded as more transparent and consumer-oriented, thereby further strengthening their positive reputation and fostering trust among consumers. Consequently, UGC emerges as a pivotal instrument within content marketing strategies employed by MSMEs, facilitating the continuous cultivation of consumer trust and loyalty. The impact of content generated by consumers, such as reviews, photographs, or videos demonstrating product usage, on brand trust is also significant. Research indicates that 72% of consumers place more trust in UGC than in traditional advertising.

The findings of the study demonstrate a robust correlation between consumer engagement and brand trust within the context of MSME content marketing. The study found that high levels of engagement, such as interactions through comments, likes, shares, and direct messages on social media, not only reflect the audience's interest in the content presented, but also play an important role in building a more personal and transparent relationship between brands and consumers. The study revealed that when MSMEs respond to questions, comments, or feedback from consumers in a timely and empathetic manner, it fosters a sense of appreciation and care from consumers, thereby strengthening their brand trust. The frequency with which consumers engage with relevant and quality content directly correlates with their sense of brand proximity, thereby fostering deeper loyalty and enhancing trust. In summary, active and responsive engagement by MSME brands is indicative of a brand's consideration for its audience, thereby fostering positive perceptions and fortifying consumer trust. A positive correlation has been observed between the level of engagement, measured by likes, comments, and shares, and brand trust. It has been observed that brands that proactively engage with consumers on social media platforms have been able to enhance the perception of trust by up to 30% in comparison with brands that adopt a more passive approach.

The findings of the study indicate that consumer testimonials and reviews play a pivotal role in fostering brand trust for MSMEs. This is due to the fact that both provide social proof, which in turn increases brand credibility in the eyes of potential customers. Consumers have a propensity to place greater trust in the genuine experiences of others who have utilized a product or service, as opposed to the assertions made by the brand itself. The study revealed that honest reviews, accompanied by visual evidence of the product in use, such as photographs or videos, can reinforce positive perceptions and enhance the level of trust in the product or brand. Testimonials that detail positive experiences can influence purchasing decisions, while negative reviews, when addressed effectively by the brand, can demonstrate transparency and a commitment to enhancing the quality of the product or service. Utilizing consumer testimonials and reviews is a strategic method for MSMEs to cultivate a more authentic and trustworthy brand image, which in turn can facilitate the expansion of their customer base and enhance consumer loyalty. Consumer testimonials play a pivotal role in fostering trust. Research indicates that testimonials with substantiating evidence, such as before-and-after photographs of product usage, are more effective in fostering trust than brand claims alone.

The findings of the study indicate that collaboration programs with influencers exert a substantial influence on the establishment of brand trust for MSMEs. Influencers are frequently regarded as possessing high credibility and the capacity to reach a more extensive and specialized audience. This strategy has been successfully implemented by MSME Ghidza Sasuke, who collaborated with local influencer Ella Arsyad to cultivate consumer trust, particularly among the influencer's followers. The strategic collaboration with influencers, particularly those who possess an audience pertinent to MSME products or services, has been demonstrated to fortify brand image and enhance consumer trust. This is primarily due to the perception of influencers as autonomous and trustworthy entities. The study found that when influencers share their personal experiences with MSME products or services, audiences tend to trust the recommendations more, because they are considered honest and authentic testimonials. Furthermore, micro-influencers, characterized by smaller but more engaged audiences, have demonstrated a propensity to cultivate more intimate and personal connections with their followers. This, in turn, has been shown to exert a more substantial influence on brand trust. By leveraging these collaborative opportunities, MSMEs can augment their reach, enhance brand visibility, and cultivate greater trust among potential consumers. Collaboration with influencers or other business partners is also considered effective in strengthening trust. The endorsement of products or services by micro-influencers, perceived as more authentic, has been identified as a significant factor in fostering brand credibility among new audiences.

Discussion

Digital marketing is now the backbone of many small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in increasing visibility and strengthening relationships with customers (Al Hafiz et al., 2024). One of the increasingly popular digital marketing strategies that has proven to be effective in achieving this goal is content marketing. Content marketing involves creating and distributing relevant, valuable, and consistent content to attract, retain, and grow relationships with audiences (Lieb, 2012). Especially for MSMEs, which are often limited by resources, content marketing is an efficient option for building brand trust with a wider and more diverse audience.

Trust is the key to building long-term relationships with consumers (Srivastava, 2021). Consumers who feel trust in a brand tend to be more loyal, make repeat purchases, and even recommend products or services to others. For MSMEs, building brand trust is not an easy task, but with the right approach in content marketing, this can be achieved gradually. Authentic and transparent content can create a strong sense of trust in the eyes of consumers. Consumer trust is the main foundation in building brand loyalty, especially in the context of MSMEs who often compete with big brands (Hasanuddin Remmang, 2021). In digital marketing strategies, trust built through content marketing includes transparency, honesty, and consistency in conveying brand values. Consumers who feel trust in a brand tend to be more loyal because trust creates a sense of security and confidence that the brand will continue to provide quality products or services. Research shows that relevant, informative, and authentic content strengthens consumer trust, which ultimately drives loyalty in the form of

repeat purchases, brand support through recommendations and willingness to engage in voluntary brand promotion. This is in line with previous research which states that trust not only improves long-term relationships with customers but also builds a solid consumer community, which is an asset for MSMEs in a competitive market (Muslimah et al., 2021).

Content marketing plays an important role in building brand trust for MSMEs because the content shared provides a clear picture of brand values, product quality, and the company's commitment to customers (Komala et al., 2024). Relevant and informative content provides added value to consumers without being pushy to make a sale, which makes the audience feel more valued and understood. This study shows that audiences who engage with relevant content are more likely to trust the brand. This is supported by the opinion of previous researchers who stated that the effectiveness of content marketing in building brand trust for MSMEs lies in its ability to convey the brand's value, credibility, and honesty to the audience in an authentic and relevant manner (Wardani et al., 2024). Content designed to provide real value to consumers—such as educational information, solutions to problems, or compelling stories—can create strong emotional connections and build trust. Additionally, social proof elements, such as customer reviews, testimonials, or user-generated content (UGC), provide external validation of a brand's quality, further reassuring potential customers (Bigne et al., 2021). The study is in line with previous research showing that MSMEs that use content marketing strategies with high consistency, adjust the format and type of content to the needs of the audience, and choose the right distribution platform, are more successful in building consumer trust. This trust is a key element in increasing customer loyalty, conversion, and brand reputation in a competitive market. Content marketing also provides flexibility for MSMEs to stay relevant to evolving consumer trends and needs, making it a highly effective and sustainable strategy (Khaira et al., 2022).

Types of content that are effective in building brand trust for MSMEs include educational content, customer testimonials, storytelling, and user-generated content (UGC) (Weber et al., 2021). Educational content, such as blog articles, infographics, or video tutorials, provides consumers with relevant and useful information, demonstrating that the brand understands their needs and has expertise in the field. Customer testimonials and reviews provide social proof that strengthens a brand's credibility by showing other consumers' positive experiences. Storytelling, which illustrates a brand's values, journey, and mission, helps create an emotional connection with the audience and increases their engagement (Rašković & Nagar, 2024). Meanwhile, UGC, such as photos, videos, or reviews from customers that are reshared by brands, demonstrate transparency and increase the brand's sense of authenticity in the eyes of consumers. All of these types of content, when used consistently and tailored to the preferences of the target audience, contribute significantly to building solid trust in MSME brands (Angelita & Kramadibrata, 2024). Based on research, the most effective types of content in building brand trust for MSMEs are educational content, customer testimonials, and visual and storytelling content. Educational content, such as blog articles, video tutorials, or infographics, provides useful and relevant information to the audience (Bastomi & Safitri, 2022). Customer testimonials and reviews also provide social proof that strengthens brand credibility. In addition, storytelling or brand stories that describe

the journey, values, and mission of the business can build emotional closeness with consumers.

Choosing the right platform to distribute content greatly influences the effectiveness of your content marketing strategy (Abid & Roy, 2024). Based on the research results, platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, and LinkedIn have proven to be the most effective for MSMEs in reaching audiences and building brand trust. Instagram and Facebook, with their visual features, are perfect for products that require attractive visualizations, while YouTube is very effective for video tutorial content or more in-depth product reviews. LinkedIn is more effective for MSMEs that operate in the B2B sector or those that offer professional and technical products. Effective digital platforms for content marketing in building MSME brand trust are Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, and LinkedIn, depending on the characteristics of the audience and brand goals. Instagram and Facebook are the main choices for MSMEs because of their strong visual capabilities, such as images and short videos, which are perfect for showcasing products or creating brand stories (Utami, 2021). YouTube excels at distributing more in-depth video content, such as tutorials, product reviews, or brand journey documentation, which provides rich and engaging information. Meanwhile, LinkedIn is effective for B2B or professional-focused SMEs, with an informative article-based approach or industry discussions. In addition, platforms like TikTok are also starting to show effectiveness in engaging younger audiences with creative, short-form content (Priatama et al., 2021). Research shows that selecting the right platform, based on audience demographics and preferences, is critical to ensuring that content is well received, increases engagement, and strengthens brand trust.

Consistency in posting content and the right frequency is very important to maintain a relationship with the audience (Frijters & Geradts, 2022). Research shows that SMEs that post content regularly, such as three to four times a week, tend to have higher engagement rates. In addition, consistency in delivering messages and maintaining the quality of content helps create a stable and trustworthy brand image. Infrequent or irregular posts can make the audience feel less connected to the brand and potentially lower trust levels (Srivastava, 2021). Frequency and consistency of posting are important elements of an effective content marketing strategy to build brand trust for SMEs. Research shows that posting regularly on a schedule that fits with your audience's habits, helps keep your brand in the minds of consumers without coming across as pushy. Consistency in tone, visuals, and messaging also creates a solid, recognizable brand identity. For example, posting two to three times a week on platforms like Instagram or Facebook is considered sufficient to stay relevant without overwhelming your audience. This consistency demonstrates a brand's commitment to its audience and increases the perception of professionalism. However, it is important for SMEs to ensure that each post is high quality and relevant, as frequency without quality can damage trust. With this approach, SMEs can maintain audience engagement and build lasting relationships (Wahyudi et al., 2024).

Storytelling or telling stories through content plays an important role in building emotional connections with the audience (Yang & Zhang, 2022). Content that tells a story about how MSME brands started to grow, the challenges they faced, and how they tried to

provide solutions for customers tends to be more easily accepted by audiences. Research shows that audiences trust brands that have authentic and transparent stories, as this adds a human dimension to the brand. Storytelling makes brands feel closer and more real to consumers. Storytelling plays a crucial role in building MSME brand trust because of its ability to create a deep emotional connection between the brand and the audience (Sagita & Rafida, 2022). By telling authentic stories, such as the background of the business, the struggles behind the product, or real customer testimonials, SMEs can show their human side and core values. Personal and relatable stories make consumers feel closer and understand the brand on a deeper level, creating a sense of engagement and trust. Storytelling also helps brands differentiate themselves in a competitive market by highlighting their unique identity (Susilowati & Rahmanto, 2024). Research shows that storytelling-based content increases engagement and encourages consumers to trust brands more because they see not just the product, but also the story and purpose behind it. In other words, storytelling turns transactions into meaningful relationships between consumers and brands.

Educational content has a huge influence in increasing brand trust for MSMEs (Damayanti & Primandhana, 2024). Consumers are more likely to trust brands that not only market products, but also provide useful and relevant information to their needs. Articles, videos, or webinars that provide insight or solutions to consumer problems show that the brand cares and has expertise in its field (Astuti & Rinwantin, 2024). Research shows that consumers who feel empowered with knowledge through educational content will be more loyal and trust the brand more. Educational content plays a significant role in increasing consumer trust in MSME brands because it shows the brand's competence and good intentions to provide added value to its audience. By providing relevant, useful, and solution-oriented information, such as tutorials, practical tips, product usage guides, or industry insights, MSMEs can position themselves as a trusted source in their field (Al Hafiz et al., 2024). Educational content helps build credibility, as consumers are more likely to trust brands that demonstrate in-depth knowledge and care about their needs. Additionally, this type of content encourages active audience engagement, such as through comments, questions, or sharing information. Research shows that consistency in presenting educational content also creates long-term loyalty, as consumers feel they are getting direct benefits beyond the product or service being offered. Thus, educational content not only builds trust but also strengthens the emotional and intellectual connection between consumers and MSME brands.

User-Generated Content (UGC) plays a big role in building brand trust for MSMEs because consumers tend to trust other people's experiences more than claims made by the brand itself (Bigne et al., 2021). UGC, such as reviews, photos, and videos from customers showing how they use a product, provides social proof that strengthens a brand's credibility. Research shows that brands that actively leverage UGC can demonstrate transparency, increase consumer trust, and expand their audience reach. User-Generated Content (UGC) acts as a powerful social proof in building trust for SMB brands because it shows real experiences from other consumers, which is more authentic than direct promotional content from the brand. UGC includes photos, videos, reviews, or testimonials created by customers and shared through digital platforms, such as social media or review sites (Kalyan, 2024). This

content provides external validation that a product or service meets expectations, making potential customers more confident in choosing that brand. Research shows that consumers are more likely to trust reviews or recommendations from fellow users than traditional marketing claims. Additionally, UGC helps SMEs build a more connected and loyal consumer community, as consumers feel valued when their content is used or appreciated by brands (Sadhu et al., 2024). By leveraging UGC, SMEs not only strengthen trust, but also increase brand engagement and visibility organically.

High engagement, such as comments, likes, and shares on published content, is closely related to increased brand trust. Consumers who interact with brand content feel more valued and personally connected to the brand (Rohit et al., 2024). Research shows that the higher the level of engagement, the more likely consumers are to trust and be loyal to a brand. Therefore, MSMEs need to ensure that they not only produce engaging content but also actively respond and interact with their audiences to build stronger relationships. Engagement and trust have a close relationship in building MSME brands through content marketing strategies (Akter et al., 2024). Consumer engagement levels—such as likes, comments, sharing content, and participating in discussions—not only reflect their attention to content, but also indicate the extent to which a brand has successfully built an emotional connection with its audience. Positive interactions, such as a quick and friendly response from an SME to a comment or question, strengthen consumer trust because they feel heard and valued. Engagement also serves as public validation of a brand's reputation, where the activity of other consumers has a positive influence on potential customers who are still on the fence (Moghimi, 2024). Research shows that consistently driving engagement through relevant, interactive, and value-based content helps increase customer loyalty, as trust is built on experiences that consistently engage and delight consumers. Thus, high engagement is not only an indicator of content effectiveness, but also an important pillar in building solid trust.

Testimonials and reviews from consumers have a big impact on brand trust. Content that contains real experiences from customers can strengthen the trust of potential consumers who are still hesitant to buy products or use MSME services (Sudarsono, 2020). Research shows that customers are more likely to purchase products that have positive reviews from other users, especially if the reviews are accompanied by images or videos of the product being used. Therefore, SMEs should encourage customers to provide reviews and use these testimonials to increase brand credibility. Consumer testimonials and reviews play a key role in building brand trust for SMEs, as they provide real and independent social proof of the quality of the product or service being offered (Sudarsono, 2022). Positive reviews from satisfied customers not only serve as personal recommendations, but also serve as testimonials that strengthen a brand's credibility in the eyes of potential consumers. Consumers tend to trust the experiences of others who share similar needs and preferences, making reviews and testimonials an effective tool for overcoming doubts and building relationships of trust. Research shows that consumers are more likely to trust reviews that are transparent and honest, including constructive criticism, because it shows that the brand is receptive to feedback and committed to improvement. By featuring customer testimonials across digital channels—such as websites, social media, and e-commerce platforms—SMBs

can increase their visibility, strengthen their relationships with a wider audience, and ultimately build a strong brand reputation (Kurniati & Anastuti, 2023). The presence of consistent, positive reviews helps create a sense of security for new customers, who are more likely to make a purchase after seeing social proof supporting the quality and reliability of a product or service.

Collaboration with influencers is an effective content marketing strategy in building brand trust for MSMEs. Influencers, especially those with audiences relevant to MSME products or services, can help increase brand credibility and reach (Anjani & Irwansyah, 2020). Research shows that influencers who are perceived as authentic and have a close relationship with their followers can have a positive impact on brand image. Influencers who share positive experiences with MSME products can strengthen consumer trust and encourage purchasing actions. Collaboration programs with influencers play a vital role in building MSME brand trust, as influencers have a loyal follower base and are trusted by their audience (A. Kurniawan, 2024). When influencers who are relevant to an SME's target audience promote products or services through authentic content, they provide strong external validation of the brand's quality and value. The influence that influencers wield helps increase brand awareness, expand market reach, and more quickly create an emotional connection between brands and consumers. Additionally, because influencers' followers often feel connected to them on a personal level, influencer recommendations can reduce scepticism and increase trust in SME brands (Musa et al., 2024). Research shows that influencers who are perceived as authentic and honest, and who share the same values as a brand, can increase positive perceptions and lead to higher purchases. This type of collaboration not only introduces a product to a new audience but also strengthens existing trust by building credibility through a respected third party.

Transparency is one of the key elements in building brand trust. Consumers today increasingly value brands that are open about their products, production processes, pricing policies, and values (Angelita & Kramadibrata, 2024). Research shows that MSMEs that actively disclose clear and accountable information, especially in terms of product quality and service, are more likely to build consumer trust. Transparency creates an honest and reliable brand image, which in turn increases customer loyalty. Transparency in content marketing plays a very important role in building MSME brand trust, as consumers increasingly value openness and honesty from the brands they choose. In this context, transparency means that brands openly share information about the product manufacturing process, raw materials used, prices, return policies, and corporate social responsibility (Nabilah et al., 2021). When MSMEs present this information honestly and openly, consumers feel more confident and secure in making purchasing decisions. In addition, transparency in communicating about issues or challenges faced by the brand also shows integrity and a commitment to continuous improvement. Research shows that transparent brands tend to be more valued and chosen by consumers, especially in a market that is increasingly saturated with choices. Content that emphasizes the value of transparency—such as articles about sustainability or behind-the-scenes videos—can strengthen relationships with customers and build long-term loyalty.

Thus, transparency is not only an ethical practice, but also an effective strategy in creating lasting trust between MSME brands and their audiences (Nirwana & Biduri, 2021).

Although content marketing has many benefits, its implementation often faces various obstacles. Many MSMEs are hampered by limited resources, both in terms of time, energy, and budget (Wijoyo, 2021). Not a few MSMEs have difficulty producing quality content consistently, especially because they do not have a trained marketing team or sufficient budget to produce professional content. Other obstacles include a lack of knowledge about digital marketing techniques and difficulty in measuring the effectiveness of published content. Obstacles in implementing content marketing for MSMEs are often related to limited resources, both in terms of time, manpower, and budget. Many MSMEs have difficulty producing quality content consistently because they do not have a large enough digital marketing team or sufficient budget for professional content production (Watulandi, 2024). Additionally, selecting the right type of content and effective platforms can be challenging, especially with changing trends and audience preferences. Many SMEs also struggle to produce content that is not only engaging, but also educates and builds trust in the long term. Furthermore, without a deep understanding of analytics and content performance measurement, it is difficult for SMEs to evaluate the effectiveness of their strategies and make necessary adjustments. In addition, there is the challenge of maintaining consistency and sustainability in the content creation and distribution process, which is often hampered by the focus on core business operations (Wahyudi et al., 2024). All of these obstacles require creative solutions, such as leveraging marketing technology, collaborating with third parties (e.g. influencers), or using automation tools to manage and optimize content marketing strategies to remain effective in building brand trust.

Trust is a major factor that drives consumer loyalty to a brand. Research shows that consumers who trust a brand are more likely to make repeat purchases and participate in brand promotions. With effective content marketing, SMEs can increase consumer trust and encourage them to become loyal customers (Wardani et al., 2024). Trust is a key factor in building customer loyalty, and this is especially relevant in the context of content marketing for SMEs. When consumers feel trust in a brand, they are more likely to not only make repeat purchases but also become loyal advocates who promote the brand to others. Effective content marketing builds trust by providing consistent, transparent and valuable content, such as honest product information, testimonials from satisfied customers and authentic stories that illustrate the brand's values (Komala et al., 2024). When audiences feel that brands value them by providing useful information, listening to feedback, and consistently delivering on promises, they feel more secure and valued, which increases their desire to continue engaging with the brand. In addition, trust also influences consumers' decisions to choose products from MSMEs over large competitors, because they feel they have a personal and emotional connection with the brand (Komala et al., 2024). Research shows that loyalty built through trust can result in higher customer retention rates, increase customer lifetime value (CLV), and strengthen brand communities that actively support its growth.

It is imperative to acknowledge the moral ramifications inherent in content marketing, particularly in the context of research investigating digital marketing strategies that prioritize

the efficacy of content marketing in fostering brand trust for MSMEs in Gorontalo. A fundamental ethical consideration pertains to the act of veracity in the dissemination of information. It is imperative for content marketing initiatives to refrain from disseminating misleading data or research outcomes, such as the citation of inaccurate statistics or the generalization of findings without a robust substantiation. By providing transparent and fact-based information, brands can foster sustainable trust with their audiences.

Furthermore, content marketing must be mindful of the potential for psychological manipulation, which has the capacity to adversely impact consumers. In the context of this study, it is imperative that digital marketing strategies employed by MSMEs in Gorontalo refrain from the utilization of techniques such as excessive clickbait or the use of fictitious testimonials. An ethical approach to content marketing, exemplified by the presentation of authentic customer reviews and a genuine portrayal of the benefits associated with a product or service, is more likely to engender long-term trust and customer loyalty.

Another salient moral implication pertains to the social responsibility of content creators in presenting educational and useful content to their audience. The objective of content marketing extends beyond the mere pursuit of increased sales; it also endeavours to foster a more profound comprehension of digital strategies employed by MSMEs in Gorontalo. By presenting information that supports the ethical growth of local businesses, content marketing can serve as a tool that benefits both business owners and consumers. Specifically, it can help consumers make smarter, more ethical decisions when interacting with brands.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Content marketing plays a significant role in building brand trust, which in turn contributes to long-term customer loyalty. Through various types of relevant and authentic content, such as educational articles, video storytelling, and user-generated content (UGC), MSMEs can introduce their brand values in a way that touches the audience emotionally and rationally. This helps build positive perceptions and credibility, which are crucial for MSMEs looking to compete in an increasingly competitive market. Choosing the right digital platform greatly influences the effectiveness of a content marketing strategy. Platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, and LinkedIn provide MSMEs with the opportunity to reach a wider audience, with each platform offering features that support different content formats. Instagram and Facebook are highly effective for showcasing visual content and engaging directly with the audience, while YouTube allows for the development of more in-depth and educational video content. LinkedIn, on the other hand, is more relevant for B2B MSMEs to build credibility through knowledge-based content and professional networking.

Frequency and consistency in posting content are also important factors that cannot be ignored. By adhering to a regular schedule and presenting content that is consistent in quality and message, MSMEs can maintain their brand presence in the minds of consumers, increase engagement, and strengthen relationships with their audiences. Moreover, active consumer engagement through comments, sharing, or following invitations to interact with

the brand, also strengthens the sense of trust because consumers feel valued and recognized by the brand. Finally, the obstacles faced by MSMEs in implementing content marketing, such as limited resources, selection of content types, and ongoing strategy management, need to be overcome with a more structured approach and the use of digital tools that can help optimize results. Therefore, although content marketing is very effective in building trust and loyalty, its success depends heavily on the brand's commitment to providing quality and relevant content and engaging the audience in an authentic and caring way.

This study underlines that content marketing is an effective strategy to build brand trust for MSMEs. By utilizing various digital platforms, creating quality content, and maintaining interaction with consumers, MSMEs can strengthen their position in the market. However, this success requires dedication, innovation, and adaptation to the evolving needs of consumers. The results of this study provide a strong foundation for developing a more targeted and effective digital marketing strategy. The study recommends that MSMEs focus on creating content that is relevant to their audience, using storytelling, and utilizing data analytics to improve the effectiveness of their strategy. In addition, collaboration with more affordable micro influencers can be a strategic step.

The implications of implementing a content marketing strategy in building brand trust for MSMEs are very important in driving innovation and long-term business sustainability. By utilizing effective content marketing, MSMEs can continue to innovate in creating relevant and interesting content, adapting to changing consumer needs and preferences. Educational and authentic content not only strengthens relationships with customers but also drives innovation in products and services, as customer feedback and engagement can provide valuable insights. Sustainability is created when MSMEs are able to build strong trust with their audiences, leading to customer loyalty, long-term retention, and increased brand reputation. By paying attention to consistency, transparency, and utilizing data to optimize strategies, MSMEs can maintain their brand relevance, adapt quickly to market trends, and create a solid foundation for sustainable growth.

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